

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING SCIENCES & RESEARCH
TECHNOLOGY****REVIEW OF SOME COMPARISONS BETWEEN PHP AND ASP.NET FROM THE
VIEWPOINT OF A NOVICE PROGRAMMER****Mehak Vermani**

Asstt. Prof., Deptt. of ComputerScience, MLU DAV College, Phagwara

ABSTRACT

At the present time websites produce dynamic response to the user requests. So there is a need of dynamic web scripting languages. A webpage is server-side dynamic page whose structure is controlled by server-side scripts. The Scripting Language refers to dynamic high level general purpose language. Three are most popular web scripting languages are: PHP, JSP and ASP.NET languages in the world. The major requirements for enterprise applications are Performance, Scalability, manageability, code portability, mode of source, Cloud Feasibility, database, security are rapidly increasing. Now the issue in this competitive environment is choosing the best scripting language. Both PHP and ASP.NET are basically used for creating dynamic and interactive web sites. PHP is known as a server side scripting language, which is free, efficient and prompted by PHP community. There is a competition between ASP.NET and PHP or we can say that PHP is substitute to competitors such as Microsoft's ASP. ASP.NET is a Microsoft product and basically used for creating web sites with HTML, CSS and Java Script.. We have analyzed the results of both technologies by creating web pages and noted their response time. In this research topic, we have compared both languages on the basis of various factors.

KEYWORDS: Generation, Web Content, platform, External Hosting, CGI and Web Applications.

INTRODUCTION

Internet becomes necessary for everyone's life. The usage of internet has increased day by day, without internet life is impossible. In the era of Internet Having a website is like opening a door and inviting potential customers into your business. The main motive behind the creation of website is your customers can get to know you and view, buy your products through the website according to their need. Even when you aren't at work, your website is. Website is business card to thousands of people.. Web Applications have various applications like paying bills, social networking, email, online transactions (like purchasing and selling goods), bank transactions (debit, credit) online examination, Government and non government facilities available on internet

NEED OF WEB APPLICATIONS (WEBSITE CREATION)**Expands your reach:**

By choosing website there are no limits between the boundaries to access. Anyone can easily access at any time.

Increases the effectiveness of your advertising;

Web is dynamic while Print advertising is static, while the. Once you have a website up and running can help you get your message across at any time or any space.

Gathers feedback:

Feedback is best way to improve the business quality. There are many ways to get feedback from customer like in form of filling some kind of form, e-mail, connecting various social site are the easy way to get feedback.

Sells directly:

There is no concept of retailer and wholesaler. E-commerce can dramatically reduce expensive overhead while delivering a 24/7 services. Website gives you the opportunity your to distinguish your company or organization to your client. Even if you don't sell your product online,.

Reaching today's consumer:

Today's life is not possible without these electronics gadgets. Now Digital world needs digital world of connection. Now clients or customers creating their own decisions based on the website. A engaging website are playing role in small as well large business.

Now the major question arises, How we can achieve this goal?

There are the languages which are used for creation of website.

- ❖ **PHP**
- ❖ **ASP**
- ❖ **Python**
- ❖ **Ruby on Rails**
- ❖ **Java**
- ❖ **ColdFusion**

Another question arises ?, Which language is best ?

Survey answers this question, no such language is best. Each language or we can say technology has its own pros and cons. In this paper we have discussed only two technologies i.e. PHP and ASP.NET.

Table shows comparison between ASP.NET and PHP

Basis of Difference	Active Server Pages .NET (ASP.NET)	Hypertext Preprocessor (PHP)
Latest Stable Version	4.0	5.3.3
License cost/licensing	Costly licensing MS EULA	Free licensing PHP License v3.01
Price	ASP.NET – if .NET Framework is free. accordingly ASP.NET also free In case of Web Server – IIS – Not Free. OS cost applicable Operating System – Windows Server is not free	PHP – Free Web Server – Free OS – Linux environment is free, but in case of Window environment is costly
Development Cost	Developer cost Involved Visual Studio Express Editions are complimentary Rapid-Application-Development Model. So development takes fewer time	Developer Cost Involved Free/Open Source IDEs available Much coding involved
Code Portability	In case of PHP, a code written on Linux/Apache will work on Windows or any OS/Web Server	But .NET, multiple ports are available, you will require some twists to make it run.
Mode of source	Closed Source., because it is product of Microsoft	Open Source, it is available in free of cost
Security Fixes	Auto Update – it is the part of Operating System.	Need to update separately when available
Languages	C# VB.NET Jscript, etc.	PHP
Database	Microsoft SQL Server	MySQL
Frameworks / OOPs	There is an inbuilt framework (called web forms framework) available which will force developers to use OOPs. only standard framework available	You can write both procedural and OOPs based code Many available

Performance	Faster because ASP.NET is compiled	Faster for small programs and slower for medium-to-big programs.PHP is interpreted
Platform	Only on Windows	Multiple
External Hosting	Widely available although requires fee	Widely available with zero cost

BACKGROUND

There are majority of things that both languages can fulfill what you want. Both can be properly programmed and both run securely but also both can be programmed inadequately and be insecure. One of the first dynamic scripting languages was Common Gateway Interface (CGI). CGI provides interactivity to web applications so they can become responsive & dynamic and respond back to web browser or client application. CGI is an environment for web server that generates Pages dynamically. CGI is an intermediate link between web server and client. Whenever database queries, user submit a form CGI Script usually called but development of CGI more sophisticated, CGI is not easy to write and require more complex and designing skills at the part of web developers. If proper care is not taken, CGI program may compromise the server security

PHP which is a contraction of Hypertext Pre-processor is a server side scripting language, which follows the era of CGI basically used for producing dynamic web pages .It is a widely used general purpose scripting language which can be bounded into Hypertext Transfer Mark-up Language (HTML) source document . Afterwards, a web server it can be interpreted by with a PHP processor module generating the web document.

On other hand, Active Server Pages .NET (ASP.NET) is another web development technology developed and it is product of Microsoft. As part of the .NET Framework, ASP.NET technologies is compiled using these languages like VB.NET, C# and allow developers to build dynamic web sites, web applications and web services.

ASSUMPTIONS

The first thing that came up to mostly all developers mind that PHP is quite simple language comparing to ASP.NET which is a absolute framework that offers a extensive collection of possibilities Maybe PHP has a simple learning curve comparing to ASP.NET. But on the other hand, it doesn't mean that web designers should limit their selves just to PHP. Why not be recognizable with new technologies as well? The other thing that might be important is that PHP was always free; unlike ASP.NET paid software is needed. However, today you can build rich ASP.NET applications for free.

Famous WebPages (Websites) built in both technologies are given below:

There are the top websites built with PHP	There are few highest traffic website using ASP.NET MVC
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. facebook 2. Wikipedia 3. Yahoo! 4. flipkart 5. iStockPhoto 6. Flickr 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. encyclopedia.com 2. kbb.com 3. break.com 4. gettyimages.com 5. apartmentfinder.com

Response Time of ASP.NET WEB PAGE

I made web page in both technology and note their page load time, Here following diagram show the page load time of asp.net.

The screenshot displays a website interface for 'Purity'. At the top, there is a purple header with the site name 'Purity' in a cursive font and social media icons for Facebook, RSS, and Twitter. Below the header is a dark navigation bar with links for HOME, ABOUT, STAFF, SERVICES, and CONTACT, along with a search box. The main content area features a large, high-quality image of spa-related items: two rolled-up orange towels, several smooth white stones, a lit candle in a glass holder, and a wicker ball. Below this image are five article cards, each with a different background image and a colored bottom section. The cards are labeled 'Fashion 1' (green), 'Fashion 2' (yellow), 'Fashion 3' (red), 'Fashion 4' (teal), and 'Fashion 5' (purple). Each card has a 'Read More' link. A red arrow points to the 'Fashion 3' card. At the bottom of the screenshot, a status bar shows the text 'THIS PAGE TOOK 00:00:01.6444554 milliseconds TO LOAD'.

Response Time of PHP WEB PAGE

Here following diagram shows the page load time of php

Following Graphic diagram shows the load time of both PHP and ASP.NET

On both I analysis that Php page took lesser time as compare to ASP.NET

Following diagram shows th percentage of usage of server side programming

CPU UTILIZATION WHEN USE UWAMP SERVER FOR PHP

GRAPH OF CPU AFTER 2 SEC OF LOADING TIME.

Why developers hate ASP.NET??

.....why they are wrong..

Each technology has its own Pros and cons. There is a misconception that it is expensive, no doubt is Microsoft product and available in paid form but

- ASP.NET - .NET Framework is free. So that ASP.NET technology is also open
- Web Server IIS (Internet Information Server)-Not Open OS cost applicable
- OS – Windows Server – Not Free

On other hand,

- PHP – Free
- Web Server – Free

On the basis of Survey I would like to say, PHP is being constantly upgrading to subsequently level and its performance areas is really increasing these days. Community used to label PHP as most terrible language because it's poor performance and lack of API capabilities. But these misconception are of past not of today. Today PHP is much dominant like any other. According to comprehensive and vast web technology surveys, the share of PHP as Server Side Language is more than 80%... **The leading websites around run PHP, Facebook is a primary example that PHP can handle stress..**

- OS – Linux is free, Windows is costly. There is one more **misconception regarding Microsoft is that**

- Microsoft is a immense or massive software firm, and like all other corporations, they're in business to make money.

It is actually easy to get into the mindset that ASP.NET is not suitable for everything but large-scale sites. Microsoft is a platform corporation, after all, and their various factors are primarily focused towards business solutions. .NET framework is basically used for large scale business... most high level projects have made in .net framework.

CONCLUSION

Our aim was to give review of the both technology. There is no fight between the web language; the only point discussed in this paper is that in PHP runs or handle easily as well as available as open software. In some phases, these approaches may or may not be able to produce relative and desired data. To overcome these problems additional information should be gathered and new attempt should be made to get relative data. Our aim was to give review of the both technologies. This paper tends to examine and compare the performance factors of ASP.NET as well as PHP 5.3.0 frameworks. Two web applications was developed i.e. Two web pages are developed using these two technologies and note their load time.. Both applications give their best result. The consequence shows that the requests take minimum time to perform any task on both frameworks. But we have seen response time of PHP is lesser than ASP.NET and PHP has a good performance. However, in stress test PHP server also performed better than ASP.NET with the response time of 0.03s and 0.06s respectively. In case memory and CPU utilization PHP also performed better than ASP.NET. In conclusion, the test result shows that PHP works best out of the two scripting languages.

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